

THE LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF BÈKWÁRRA BY BÈKWÁRRA INDIGINES IN YORÙBÁ LAND

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17038588>

Keywords:

*Lexico-Grammar,
Honorific
Pronouns, Code-
Mixing/Switching,
Lexico-Semantics,
Tone
Misplacement*

Abstract: *This paper presents a sociolinguistic study of the variety of Bèkwárra language spoken by Bèkwárra children born in the Western part of Nigeria—Yorùbá land— and explores its distinct features. The study examines the concepts of First Language (L1), Mother Tongue (MT), and Second Language (L2), with a focus on how these apply to the linguistic reality of these children. Linguistic features analyzed include lexico-grammar, lexico-semantics, honorific pronouns, and tone misplacement, along with the resulting semantic ambiguities. The study argues that achieving competence in Bèkwárra as an L2 depends largely on the role of parents and adult speakers within the speech community. However, many of these adults now prioritize mastering Yorùbá—the dominant language of their immediate environment—resulting in minimal linguistic guidance for the younger generation. Consequently, Bèkwárra children in Yorùbáland often acquire the language with little or no support. This paper recommends that adult speakers and parents consistently use Bèkwárra when interacting with younger (L2) speakers to ensure intergenerational transmission and linguistic continuity.*

Introduction

There are certain rules that determine standard and non-standard language, and they are applicable to almost all the languages of the

world—except where (if possible, the idea of bilingualism/multilingualism) is not involved. These include grammatical rules, syntactic rules, and phonological rules. These rules are naturally

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Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 9; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 5.37

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

built into native speakers of every language, but they are learned and acquired by second language users. Varieties of language develop for a number of reasons: differences can arise due to geographical factors; people who live in different geographic areas often develop distinct dialects... (Norquist, 2024).

The variety of Bèkwárà language spoken or used in the western part of Nigeria by

Bèkwárà indigenes who acquired Yorùbá as their Mother Tongue (MT) or First Language (L1) has certain features which distinguish it from its standard form. These features break the standard Bèkwárà grammatical, syntactic, and phonological rules, commonly manifesting at the lexico-grammatical level, lexicosemantic level, and at the phonological level (accent), which often leads to wrong interpretations of meanings in their conversations. In most cases, these indigenes, who are now L2 speakers of Bèkwárà, code-switch between Yorùbá and Bèkwárà and code-mix lexical items (words) in Yorùbá with the Bèkwárà language.

Their linguistic competence and performance, as propounded by Chomsky, are seen in their social use of the Yorùbá language; they have greater linguistic competence in the Yorùbá language. To measure their level of competence in the first language, which is Yorùbá, one has to consider or study how these speakers bring Yorùbá grammatical forms into the Bèkwárà language and use Bèkwárà to construct syntactically correct grammatical structures far better than

when they rely only on Bèkwárà. For example, when you ask a question like *ibang ngã*, which means *What is it?*, instead of responding *iyem ngã re*, they will tell you *iyire*, which is a direct translation of the Yorùbá word *kò sí*.

First Language (L1), also known as the Native Language, is the only language of a monolingual person, which is acquired naturally in their native environment and which meets all their linguistic needs. Mother Tongue (MT) is usually the sequentially first language of a bi/multilingual person. Occasionally, a sequential language could become a mother tongue if it assumes the role of a mother tongue, as in the case when a Yorùbá–English bilingual who was born in and grew up in

England uses English for most of their needs without having any recourse to using Yorùbá. In Nigeria, for instance, Yorùbá, Hausa, and Igbo are mother tongues for the Yorùbá, Hausa, and Igbo cultural groups.

Second Language (L2), on its own, is defined as a language which is usually the sequentially second language of a bilingual person; it may be the third or fourth language of a bilingual individual, which, however, functions as a second language in societal bilingualism (Akindele & Adegbite, 1999:48–49).

This paper attempts a cursory look into these linguistic features, with much attention on the phonological feature.

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Varieties of Bèkwárra Language

There are primarily three varieties of Bèkwárra language. We have the standard form, which is used or spoken by the Bèkwárra people whose Mother Tongue (L1) is Bèkwárra, and the other two varieties, which are spoken by Afrike and Utugwang, and are said to be dialects of Bèkwárra (Onigah, 2023:34). Apart from these, there are other sub-varieties such as the Lagos, Akure/Ondo, Kaduna, Enugu/Aba, and Abuja varieties. The major feature noticeable among these speakers is the accent. They speak according to the language of the immediate environment where they were born or raised. In this case, we have such varieties as mentioned above.

In this research work, we noticed that not only the speakers who were born outside Bèkwárra (e.g., Lagos, Akure, Abuja, Enugu, etc.) have this problem. Some of their parents also encounter

pronunciation difficulties after long-term linguistic contact with other languages like Yorùbá, Hausa, or Igbo. Some of the elders said age is responsible for it, while others said they are far from the language in terms of using it for everyday conversations.

FEATURES OF L₂ SPEAKERS OF BEKWARRA LANGUAGE IN WESTERN NIGERIA (AKURE)

Lexico-Grammatical Feature

There are several ways by which non-standard grammatical structures or expressions manifest in the standard organization of sentences in the Bèkwárra language. These features include, among others: the transfer of Yórùbá forms into Bèkwárra, the use of honorific pronouns for elders (which is not found in the Bèkwárra language), and code-mixing and code-switching between the two languages.

Examples of forms transfer:

1. Questions: Ibang ngã? 'What is it?'

L₂ Response

Iyire

'it is not'

Standard

iyem ngã re

'It is nothing'

In Bèkwárra language, *iyi* is the possibility of being available but cannot answer the question *ibang ngã?* The correct answer to this question is the phrase *iyem ngã re*. *iyire* is a direct word for word translation of the standard Yorùbá word, *kòsí*.

2. Okwuna yi kaa?

Okwuna kinkin iyi re

'There is no one/single cocoyam'

'Is there cocoyam?'

okwuna yi ka re

'There is no cocoyam'

In example 2, the L₂ speaker again translated the word *Kankan* from standard Yorùbá into Bèkwárra as *kinkin*, emphasizing negation, whereas, the correct phrase should be *yi ka re*.

The use of Honorific Pronouns

Plural pronouns like *you* and *they* are used in Yorùbá language to refer to an elderly (senior) persons and leaders (Bamgbose, 1966; Awobuluyi, 1978). Also, in offices, employees often refer to their senior colleagues as *you* (plural) for a singular person and *they*, even when the subject is singular. It is a socio-cultural sign of respect. Those who speak Bèkwárra as second language (L₂) within the *Yorùbá states*, speaking Yorùbá as their first language often apply this to Bèkwárra language.

For example:

Standard Bèkwárra

L₂

3. Abuo

amin abuo

‘welcome’

‘you (pl) welcome’

You (sgl) are welcome

you (pl) are welcome

The idea of honorific pronoun in example 3 above is a direct transfer of linguistic feature from Yorùbá language. *e* is a plural pronoun and it is used in greeting as in 3 above. *E kaabo*; meaning *you (pl) are welcome*, even though the subject is singular. It is a sign of respect.

4. Be jiriji

e be jiriji

‘Come and eat food’

‘come (pl) and eat food’

This is similar to the example given in 3 above; it does not matter whether the speaker is referring to one or two people, he or she just wants to make sure that respect is given to whom it is due but it is only permitted in the Yorùbá language. Therefore you can say *e wá jẹun*. Whereas, *e be jiriji* in Bèkwárra language means that the subject or listeners are more than one.

5. O tum bé ma?

Amin e tum bé ma?

Have you (sgl) come back?

Have you (pl) come back?

In Yorùbá language, *o* is a singular pronoun but by culture, it is not used for seniors or elders; rather, *e* is used for seniors and elders (Ajayi and Balogun, 2014). The speaker in example 5 therefore applied the same linguistic principle or rule to Bèkwárra, referring to one person as *amin* which is a plural pronoun used for many.

Code-Mixing and Code-Switching

The idea of code-mixing and code-switching in bilingual or multilingual speeches could be traced to the time that human beings began to acquire two or more languages in addition to their first language

(Muysken, 2000). That is why Ezech et al (2022:107) opine that ‘the phenomena of code switching and code mixing are as old as the culture of bilingualism and multilingualism’. As far as second language learning is concerned, code-mixing and code-switching cannot be overemphasized. This however, only manifest in spoken language. ‘However, code switching and mixing are commonly studied as elements of spoken language, involving the alternation of codes’ (Ezeh et al).

This manifests when these L₂ speakers of Bèkwárra language bring in lexical item from Yorùbá and insert it in-between words or phrases, or when the speakers switch from Bèkwárra to Yorùbá and vice versa. The switch sometimes permits speakers to join two clauses, one from each of the two languages. It may be at the beginning, middle or at the end of sentence. From the data collected from the field of research, let us look at the following examples:

Bèkwárra Yorùbá

6. Ng dee kung faa he / şùgbọ́ n kò sí iná.

‘I wanted to roast it but there was no fire’

This sentence in a standard Bèkwárra will be, *ng dee kung fáá he ayinikin ine yi re* which has the same meaning with the code-switched sentence in 6 above. In Bèkwárra language, the negative marker *re* occurs at sentence final position unlike *kosi* in Yorùbá. This may also cause a little challenge for the speaker who is still building up his language competence.

Bèkwárra Yorùbá

7. Ng bá gwa ebetuo / şùgbọ́ n mi ò lówó lọ́ wọ́

‘I will drink wine but I don’t have money’

Example 7 is made up of two simple sentences conjoined using *şùgbọ́ n*, a Yorùbá word, meaning *but*. *Ng bá ngwa ebètuo* is a complete sentence in Bèkwárra meaning ‘I will drink wine’ or ‘I want to drink wine’, and *mi ò lówó* as used here means ‘I don’t have money’. Whereas, the correct sentence in Bèkwárra should be, *Ng bá gwa ebetuo ayinikin ng yi r’ une re* The speaker successfully switched between the two languages and still retained its semantic implication.

Bèkwárra Yorùbá Bèkwárra

8. De ìyàwó dee I bé

Tell wife that she comes

‘Tell my wife to come’

This statement does not necessary mean that a man is calling his wife; the family members contextually refer to every woman married into the family as their wife. Here, the speaker code-mixed lexical items, starting a sentence with Bèkwárra, inserting Yorùbá and ended it with Bèkwárra. This shows how

linguistically skillful the speaker is. The sentence should be *de unyaraba dee I bé*. The problem in this example could be that the speaker could not pronounce *unyarabá* or could not remember it in time so he opted for *ìyàwó*, a Yorùbá word with the same meaning.

Bèkwárra

Yorùbá

9. Chúchu kem

owó

‘Please give me money’. *Chuchu kem* means ‘please give me’ and *owó* in Yorùbá means ‘money’. The correct sentence is *chúchu kem une*.

Lexico-Semantic Feature

This manifests mostly at the level of tone placement because Bèkwárra language is a tonal language; L₂ speakers find it difficult to pronounce some tonal segments which always results in wrong semantic implications. Examples are shown below:

Standard form	Gloss	L ₂ users	Gloss
10. O jì riji	‘you (sgl) ate food’	O jì riji	‘you (sgl) stole food’
11. A jì riji	‘he/she ate food’	A jì riji	‘he/she stole food’
12. Faa mi	‘teach me’	fàà me	‘grind me’
13. Ng nyie àlu	‘I bought a shirt’	Ng nyié alu	‘I knew a shirt’
14. Kem ungwofaa	‘give me a teaspoon’	kem ungwofàà	‘give me a chick’
15. Kp’ ufiá angĩn	‘take this soup’	kp’ ufià ngĩn	‘take a slave here’

In example 15, *ufiá* means ‘soup’ while *ufià* with a low tone means ‘a slave’.

16. Itúng í nuo mi kin ‘I am hungry’ itùng i nuo mi kin ‘I am thirsty for a fight’

Tone Misplacement/problem

This can also be referred to accent problem. The most common feature of L₂ speakers of language is the phonological feature.

Standard	Gloss	L ₂ Speakers	Gloss
17. Umo	‘water’	Umó (Afrike pronunciation)	‘water’
18. Ebèchié	‘Tears’ (liquid from the eyes)	Èbéchié	‘cocoyam’

The L₂ will say, *Ng ba ja èbéchié* instead of *èbéchié*

19. Ikúng	‘termite’	ikùng	‘owl’
20. Ologo	‘cassava’	ológo (from Yorùbá)	‘a glorious Person’
21. Ikwùn	‘fresh, wet’	ikwun	‘beating, punishment’

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Volume: 9; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 5.37

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

22. Ikwèn	‘fish’	ikwén	‘firewood’
23. Ufo	‘tomorrow’	ùfó	‘ghost’
24. Itáng	‘seed’	itang	‘floor, grand’
25. uchì	‘judgement’	uchi	‘tree’

It is important to state here that the meanings of L₂ expressions are contextually determined rather than depending on their semantic meanings. The L₂ speakers hardly pronounce these words correctly in connected speech but sometimes, they may achieve ninety percent pronunciation when these words are mentioned in isolation.

Conclusion

We gathered that these L₂ speakers of the Bèkwárra language develop in their language competence as they grow, usually around the age of 20 and above, but their intonation will always show that they are not native speakers, no matter how hard they try to improve in their language learning. At this age, they speak the language better compared to when they were below 16. As a matter of fact, their improvement in the language depends largely on their parents and relatives who are native speakers of the Bèkwárra language. We discovered that as the children depend on parents and relatives for their language learning and improvement, the adults too—who are supposed to help them attain more proficiency—are struggling to improve their competence in the Yorùbá language, thereby

losing competence in the Bèkwárra language gradually.

The only solution is that the adults should be encouraged to speak Bèkwárra more often with their children, rather than using the Yorùbá language for their daily interactions.

Acknowledgement

I give thanks to God almighty, the author and finisher of our faith. I sincerely appreciate Ejim Okoh; his wife, Mrs. Cecelia Okoh; and their children who were my major respondents. Though these speakers were not specifically consulted for this research purpose, the researcher (being a native speaker of Bekwarra) spent some weeks with these speakers while collecting his data. I can't forget my colleague, Ogunyale W.J. of the Department of Linguistics and Languages, University of Uyo, for his encouragement.

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International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

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